

Strategy and vision for building European technological sovereignty in 5G and beyond

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It is clear today, when observing the telecommunication and microelectronics ecosystems, that Europe faces significant challenges to maintain leadership. At the same time, the stakes have never been higher. As the first commercial 5G networks are being rolled out, the world is experiencing global threats such as climate change, pandemics, social inequalities, unemployment, and distrust of information.

Investments that turn these challenges into opportunities are apparent winners. Disregarding how this ambiguity eventually will unfold, the fundamental role of evolved digital infrastructure and related technologies have already been identified. China and the US are currently acting to secure a high degree of autonomy across the whole telecommunication value chain, including components for 5G connectivity systems.

This is not by coincidence. Like roads, power grids, and other necessary infrastructure that once propelled societies in the 1900s, digitalization will do the same for this century. However, the roads towards future prosperity are not made of asphalt, they are spelled waveguides and wireless.

As a result, Europe must invest now to be a frontrunner in evolved 5G and 6G networks. To accomplish this, the European industries in telecommunication, microelectronics, and connectivity-enabled verticals must come together and coordinate joint actions with a strategic value chain approach in mind.

The COREnect project has during its initial phase identified technology gaps in the European ecosystem. These represent critical factors in sustaining leadership in the race towards 6G and can summarize the European position as follows:

European strengths

- Leading position on the cellular infrastructure market
- Strong IDM* players with local connectivity solution portfolios and derivative technology offerings
- Leading position on the local connectivity market
- Strong MCU** ecosystem well suited for IoT and 6G use cases

European weaknesses

- No position on the consumer cellular connectivity market
- No advanced CMOS manufacturing facilities
- Disability to develop advanced CPU or AI accelerators
- Limited SoC design capability using advanced manufacturing processes available in Asia

In the future, the COREnect project and associated expert groups will focus on strategic measures to address the weak spots by leveraging on the strengths mentioned above. This includes investment proposals, coordination actions, and the role of different private and public entities.

The goal is not to reach complete autonomy but to secure long term European relevance in the global ICT ecosystem. Given the road towards a fully connected world, such investments will fuel job creation across all European business segments and industry verticals.

* *Integrated device manufacturer*

** *Microcontroller unit*